

Exploring the Emerging Perspectives from the NEP on the Integration of AI in Higher Education

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India's National Education Policy, launched in July 2020, emphasises five elements for education enhancement: affordability, equity, accountability, accessibility, and quality. It intends to enhance the structure of online education, open and distance learning, and expand technological adoption in education, which will further lead to the development of the complete persona and mindset of students. NEP is an inclusive framework aimed at the elementary-level of education to higher education in the country. New circumstances and realities require initiatives. The recent pandemic has entailed the substitution of typical in-person modes of education with modes of quality education. The use of technology in education would alter traditional classroom teaching, which would facilitate moulding the education scenario as a whole. NEP intends to adopt the use and integration of technology to enhance various aspects of education. To facilitate effective ed-tech tools in all dimensions of teaching and learning, NEP is supposed to institute the National Education Technology Forum (NETF). This paper intends to provide a theoretical background on the NEP's vision of the adoption of technology in higher education in India.

Keywords: National Education Policy, Technology, Higher Education

1. Introduction

India's accomplishments in terms of enhancing access to quality education, increasing elementary school enrolment, increasing the number of students in schools and reducing number of out-of-school children are phenomenal (Mukherjee, D. 2010; Samariya, A. K. 2020). However, as per the 75th round household survey by NSSO in 2017-18, 50% of the primary school-going children which constituted around 50 million children, did not achieve grade-appropriate learning levels, according to the National Achievement Survey, NCERT 2017. When it comes to higher education, India's Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) is only 25.2% (Govinda, R., & Bandyopadhyay, M. 2008). India has the world's third largest higher education system in terms of students. The country has seen the establishment of a number of higher education institutions in recent years (Kumar, A. K., & Rustagi, P. 2010). However, only three Indian institutions could make it to the list of top 200 institutes of the prestigious Quacquarelli Symonds (QS) World University Rankings 2020 (Bajpai, N., & Goyal, S. 2004). This is because the education system in India has become obsolete and lacks employability and skill development owing to the low quality of education. In the view of wading through the above problems, it was crucial to reboot the education system of India (Hill, S., & Chalaux, T. 2011). For this purpose, when the whole world was going through the pandemic era, India launched its new National Education Policy in July 2020. NEP is an inclusive framework aimed at the elementary-level of education to higher education in the country. It emphasises five elements for education enhancement: affordability, equity, accountability, accessibility, and quality. NEP 2020 recommends the collaboration of technology with education in order to enhance the quality of education (Govinda, R. 2020). This paper intends to provide a theoretical background on the NEP's vision of the adoption of technology in higher education in India.

2. National Education Policy

Educational policy stresses the cultivation of personal artistic talent. A person's emotional, social, and ethical capacities and attitude and their cognitive skills are moulded by education. India's national education policy, launched on 29th July 2020, is the third NEP since India's independence (Kumar, A. 2021). NEP 2020 is based on five foundation pillars: affordability, equity, accountability, accessibility, and quality. The NEP envisions an education system that can espouse the evolution of India having a society with equitable and vibrant knowledge by giving it high-quality education. It aims to transform India into a worldwide powerhouse of wisdom by making education (both school and college) more versatile, detailed, and holistic, aiming to emphasise the exclusive abilities of each student (Kalyani, P. 2020). This policy is in alignment with the 2030 Agenda for sustainable development that has global education development as one of its goals that seeks to "ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all" by 2030 (Saxena, A. 2021). Such a soar

goal would have required the reconstruction of the entire education system to aid and promote learning. The NEP accentuates digital literacy, problem-solving, multidisciplinary, logical-reasoning, written communication, and vocational exposure in the document. The policy foresees that a profound sentiment of regard towards the fundamental duties and patriotic values must be evolved among the students by the institutions (Venkateshwarlu, B. 2021). The vision of the policy is to develop knowledge, skills, values, dispositions and a sense of pride in being an Indian to aid responsible commitment towards human rights, sustainable development and global well-being (Smitha, S. 2020).

3. Salient functions of NEP 2020

- Ensuring maximum enrolment of children at the school level: Ensuring maximum enrolment of children and their attendance at school must be the primary objective of the schooling system. Recently, it was noticed that many students are dropping out of school, and the most effective way of keeping these students enrolled at school is to provide efficient and sufficient infrastructure to ensure access to safe and engaging school education to all the students from pre-primary to Class 12. Schools must provide quality and equitable education by providing efficient counsellors and teachers (Mehta, A. C. 1994).
- Early childhood care and education with a new curricular and pedagogical structure: development of a child's cumulative brain up to 85% occurs before the age of six. This leads to the need for proper nurturing and activation of the brain in the initial years of learning, ensuring the growth of sound and a healthy brain. ECCE includes learning through creative and flexible play-based and activity-based methods. It also comprises developing social, ethical, and overall personality traits of the students. The MHRD will be in charge of the ECCE curriculum and pedagogy to ensure a keen observation of the foundational aspects of education. (Filmer, D. 2007; Handa, S. 2002).
- Attaining foundation literacy and numeracy: Foundational literacy and numeracy refer to the fundamental capacity of being able to read and understand texts and numbers and solve analogical problems. This is a crucial foundation and a vital requirement for lifelong learning. That is why it will be the priority of the government to achieve universal foundational literacy and numeracy by 2025. To serve this purpose, a National Mission on Foundational Literacy and Numeracy will be instituted by the Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD). (Laxman, R. 2024; Evans, D. K., & Hares, S. 2021; Duckworth, K., & Schoon, I. 2010).
- Amendments in school curricula and pedagogy: A 5+3+3+4 design is formulated to direct the framework for school education curricula. The structure can be understood with the help of the following table:

Table 1:5+3+3+4 design to direct the framework for school education curricula

STAGE	CLASS	CURRICULUM
Foundational stage (5 years)	3 years- pre-primary 2 years- grade 1-2	Flexible, multilevel, play/activity-based learning
Preparatory stage (3 years)	Grades- 3-5	Play, discovery, activity-based, light text books, aspects of more formal but interactive classes
Middle stage (3 years)	Grades- 6-8	Pedagogical and curricular style of foundational stage and introducing subjects for more abstract and unknown knowledge
Secondary stage (4 years)	2 years- grades 9-10 2 years- grades 11-12	Multidisciplinary study, pedagogical and curricular style of middle stage but with greater depth, critical thinking, greater flexibility and students' choice of subjects

- Multilingualism language and the power of language:** It has been observed that children grasp concepts more efficiently and quickly when they are taught the same in their mother tongue. The interactions in the classroom will be done in the mother tongue or local language of the students. The textbooks will be made available in multiple languages, including local languages. Teachers are encouraged to use a bilingual approach. The government will adopt a three-language system which will depend on the personal choice of languages of the state, and no particular language will be imposed on any state or region. Sanskrit, along with foreign languages, will also be included in the curriculum. All languages will be taught using creative, fun, experiential, and innovative methods. Indian Sign Language will be standardised across countries for students with hearing impairment (Marian, V. 2023; García, O. 2014; Grutman, R. 2019).

Equitable and inclusive education: this policy aims of bridging the social category gaps in accessing, participating and learning outcomes in school education (Shaeffer, S. 2019; Stenman, S., & Pettersson, F. 2020). Despite all the achievements in bridging gender and societal gaps at all levels of education of the Indian Education System and progressive government policies, there are still some disparities, specifically for Socio-Economically Disadvantaged Groups (SEDGs) which can broadly be categorised as:

- gender groups (particularly female and transgender individuals),
- socio-cultural groups (such as Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes, OBCs, and minorities),
- geographical groups (such as students from villages, small towns, and aspirational districts),
- disabled individuals (physical and intellectual)

Teachers–Their recruitment and deployment: Teachers occupy the most respectful position in Indian society because of their excellent knowledge and skills. However, the quality and motivation of teachers were not up to the mark. The system required a better quality of

teacher’s education, training, recruitment, deployment, work-life conditions, and empowerment. To ensure the recruitment of best quality teachers, scholarships will be provided to complete the four-year B. Ed program efficiently. To ensure the best test material, both in terms of content and pedagogy, Teacher Eligibility Tests (TETs) will be fortified. An adequate number of teachers for all subjects in schools will be ensured. Teachers’ education and training programs will be aligned with the required skills.

Standard-setting and accreditation of school education: The government must aim for complete transparency and disclosure of all finances, procedures, and educational outcomes in order to ascertain the excellence and integrity of the educational system. This is ensured by NEP, which will help in the acculturation of such structures that will aid educational institutions, teachers, and employees with sufficient aid as well as avail high quality and standard education to students of all sections of society.

4. Functions of NEP in Higher Education

A 50% increment in GER by 2035: NEP 2020 aims to augment the Gross Enrolment Ratio in higher education from 26.3% in 2018 to 50% by 2035. Higher education institutions will be aided by 3.5 Crore new seats.

Holistic and Multidisciplinary Education: Holistic and multidisciplinary education is required to lead Indian education to the 21st century and the fourth industrial revolution. It sights to evolve the intellectual, aesthetic, social, physical, emotional, and moral abilities of individuals in a consolidated manner. Such education would help to evolve students who inherit the 21st century capabilities of creativity, innovation, critical thinking, high-order thinking, problem solving, communication, and in-depth learning in the fields of arts, humanities, languages, sciences, and social sciences. India has a rich heritage of holistic and multidisciplinary education from the historical universities of Nalanda and Takshashila, which comprised learning by combining art with subjects. NEP aims to establish Departments in all fields to stimulate multidisciplinary education in India (Shukla, B., Joshi, M., Sujatha, R., Beena, T., & Kumar, H. 2022; Roy, M. A. N. O. J. I. T. 2022).

The Structure and lengths of the degree programs under NEP Under Graduate Programs

Duration of Degree	Structure
3-Year program	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> After completing 1 year in a field: a certificate after completing 2 years in a field: a diploma after completing 3 years: a degree
4-year program	Enables to explore whole range of holistic & multidisciplinary education along with the chosen subjects

Post Graduate Program

Duration of degree	Structure
2-year program	For 3-year bachelor’s program degree holders, the 2 nd year will be wholly dedicated to research
4 years bachelor’s program	One year Master’s program for the 4-year Bachelor’s program degree holders
Integrated 5-year program	Merge both bachelor’s and master’s program

- **Regulation:** The regulatory system of education is quite monotonous and disempowering which leads to limited individuals exercising immense power and lacking accountability for their actions. To tackle these issues, various functions will be carried out by different, independent, and empowered bodies under the new regulatory system of higher education in NEP. These four functions will be performed by four different constructions under a common head, that is, the Higher Education Commission of India (HECI).

- **Motivated, energised, and capable faculty:** the existence of magnificent and passionate faculty that foster excellence, creativity, and innovation is the need of the hour. For this purpose, it is crucial that the faculty be elated, passionate, involved, and ambitious to enhance their students, institutions, and professions. To achieve this, the NEP recommends the following initiatives:
 - a) Higher education institutions will provide a better work-life environment by providing amenities such as drinkable water, sanitation facilities, stationery, libraries, labs, and comfortable classroom spaces and campuses.
 - b) To reduce the burden on teachers, there will not be excessive teaching duties, and student-teacher ratios will be kept low. This will make teaching pleasant, and the teachers can invest sufficient time in the students which can enhance communication between them.
 - c) Institutions will be independent in terms of designing their own curricular and pedagogical approaches within the approved framework.
 - d) Incentives will be provided for outstanding performance in the form of rewards, promotions, recognition, and movement into institutional leadership.
- **Financial support for students:** Various measures to provide financial support to students will be adopted under the NEP. Incentives will be provided for the wellness of students belonging to underprivileged socio-cultural and socio-economic groups.
- **Setting high standards of scholarly research in all fields with the help of a new National Research Foundation:** To grow and sustain a giant and developing economy, elevating society, and an excellent country, research and knowledge creation is required. In addition to outstanding science and technology, it is crucial to have

the socio-cultural and environmental dimensions of the country to find solutions to various societal obstacles. Any country's identity, enrichment, spiritual/intellectual satisfaction, and creativity lie in the research and development of its history, art, language, and culture. NEP envisages enhancing the quality and quantity of research in India. To this end, the policy envisions a focus on scientific methods and critical thinking in learning, career counselling in schooling, promoting research in universities (including research and internships in the undergraduate curriculum), and the governance and regulatory system to promote research innovation. A National Research Foundation (NRF) will be established for the purpose of research growth and development.

- **Promotion of Indian languages, Arts and Culture:** It crucial to conserve and elevate the cultural wealth of India for the sake of the nation's identity and economy. Billions of people enjoy India's treasure trove of culture by visiting India for tourism, experiencing hospitality, admiring and shopping for Indian handicrafts, participating in Indian festivals, yoga and meditation, etc. It is essential for the promotion of students' capabilities to have cultural awareness and expression. Language is an inseparable part of culture. Language influences the way people from a particular culture communicate with others. It affects the tone, discernment of experience, and familiarity that is innate in communication among speakers of a common culture. Therefore, it is important for culture to preserve and promote its language. However, Indian languages have been neglected over a period of time, with 220 languages extinct, 197 endangered, and many severely endangered. For the purpose of preserving our treasure of languages, several steps will be taken by the policy, that is, hiring skilled language teachers both at school and college level, NRF will be funding for quality research in these areas, use of mother tongue in HEIs, and an Indian Institute of Translation and Interpretation (IITI) will be established to expand India's translation and interpretation to make high-quality study material.

Use of technology and its integration: This will be discussed in detail in the next section.

5. Use of Technology in Higher Education

Technology has the ability to revolutionise traditional learning and teaching processes. It eliminates the factors of space and time that hedge the education process which means it is required for the students to be in a particular place at a particular time to learn from the teacher. Computers and telecommunications have played a vital role in reforming higher education. Upgradation in technologies has led to alterations in the regular operations of colleges and institutions, and they are expanding their missions for the same. There has not been a single aspect of higher education that was not affected by the technological developments of the 1980s and the 1990s.

Traditionally, information was conveyed through lectures in classrooms

by professors and is discussed later. However, in the era of technology, this teaching method has become antiquated and inefficient. According to Gregory Farrington, the Web can be used to deliver a variety of information to students. This can prove to be more efficient and cost-effective. The use of technology in education can lead to a more informal environment and flexible discussions serving students' interests and queries. The application of technology would lead to active learning which enhances the learning quality of students. Technology can make teaching and learning more interactive and inspired. Technology can also make things easier for different collaborative learning groups and students who do not reside in the same geographic area and thus cannot meet in person. Technology is capable of rendering large quantities of information to the masses. This quality of technology facilitates individualisation of educational programs according to the concerns of the learner. Matthews suggests that with the technology mode of education, traditional lectures and rigid curricula have become obsolete because of their ability to personalise education according to learning interests and needs.

With the passing of the twenty-first century, there is more integration of technology in higher education. This revamped the role of professors. Professors nowadays use technology to deliver lectures, conduct research, and communicate with their students in a distant land. Professors in technology-mediated education have become more of a motivator for students to build an environment that instigates learning. They have turned into consultants and coaches. Students have to take more responsibility for their learning rather than passively absorbing information from a professor. The duties of the twenty-first century professor include the effective utilisation of instructional technology.

Advantages of integrating technology to higher education

6. New insights of the NEP 2020 for the use of technology in Higher Education

India is transforming into a digitally capable country and knowledgeable economy with the help of the Digital India Campaign. This can be achieved by collaborating education with technology. Technology improves the quality of education. In addition, technology can impact the ways students learn in classrooms with the help of new technologies. Therefore, extensive research in this area is required. To provide a platform for the free flow of ideas regarding the use of

technologies in education, NEP 2020 has envisioned an autonomous body, the National Education Technology Forum (NETF). NETF will build institutional and intellectual capabilities in technology-driven education, envisage strategic thrust in the area, forward new directions for research and innovation in the field, and provide evident-based advice to the government.

NEP recommends the following key initiatives to amalgamate technology with education at all levels (school and higher education):

Online teaching platform: The available e-learning platforms in India, such as SWAYAM and DIKSHA, will be updated to assess teachers' monitoring of student performance by providing them with an organised, appealing, and efficient set of assistive tools. Online education has gained immense popularity in recent years, and is likely to continue in the upcoming years.

Virtual labs: To help students have equal access to quality practical and hands-on experiment-based learning experiences, existing e-learning platforms such as SWAYAM, DIKSHA, and SWAYAMPURABHA will be authorised for creating virtual labs.

Pilot studies for online education: agencies, such as the NETF, CIET, NIOS, IGNOU, IITs, NITs, etc. will be regulated to conduct a series of pilot studies, in order to evaluate the advantages of collaborating education with online education while considering the downsides and also to study related areas, such as student device addiction, most preferred formats of e-content, etc. The results of these studies will be used for further improvements.

Content creation and digital depositories: NEP encourages the development of a digital depository of content which includes the creation of coursework, Learning Games & Simulations, Augmented Reality and Virtual Reality, with proper systems to receive feedback for efficiency and quality. For fun-based learning, student-appropriate tools like apps, gamification of Indian art and culture, in multiple languages, with clear operating instructions, will also be created. A reliable backup mechanism for disseminating e-content to students is provided.

Online assessment and examinations: assessment frameworks will be implemented by authorised bodies such as the proposed National Assessment Centre or PARAKH, School Boards, NTA, and other identified bodies. Research will be undertaken to find new ways to assess students using modern technologies.

Digital Infrastructure: The government has established DIKSHA which is Digital Infrastructure for Knowledge Sharing. It includes courses for teachers, quizzes, and e-content which will be aligned with the curriculum.

Adapting to artificial intelligence: The use of artificial intelligence has arisen many problems which will be kept in pace by the policy. NETF will recognise the emerging technologies and keep track of their development, potential, and disruption, and will present this report to the Education Ministry. The policy recommends creating awareness regarding the disruptive behaviour of various technologies, as well as concerns about data handling and security.

Blended models of learning: Technology learning and online

education should not replace traditional face-to-face learning. They should work complementary to each other, not as substitutes.

Addressing the digital divide: The vast population of India has limited access to digital platforms, which can make technological education difficult for them. That is why the government started educational programs which will be telecasted 24/7 on available media, such as television, radio, and community radio. These programs will be made keeping in mind all Indian languages.

Setting standards: The policy would set standards for the technology, content, and curriculum for digital learning in States, Boards, schools and school complexes, HEIs, etc.

Training and incentives for teachers: Teachers will need to reboot their ways of teaching as education shifts from traditional to technologically advanced methods. They would require training to integrate various technologies with education. Better working conditions and an increase in perks and perquisites will also encourage them to work harder as their roles have increased and credit will be taken by the technologies. That is why they have to get better with their roles.

7. National Education Technology Forum

The National Education Technology Forum (NETF) is an autonomous body that is visioned under the National Education Policy 2020 to have feedback and views about the idea of integrating technology with education. NETF will aid in choosing a course of action in terms of the initiation and implementation of technology in education by providing the required knowledge and research to the leadership of education institutions, State and Central Governments and other Stakeholders.

8. Conclusion

The paper concluded that the recent pandemic outbreak has made us realise the importance of innovative non-traditional academic pathways when archaic in-person learning was not possible. In the period when the students could not make it to their schools and colleges, technology helped to cope with the studies and the curriculum. While realising the importance of technology in education, NEP 2020 has enlisted various initiatives for the integration of technology with

education at the higher education level. It is evident from the interventions that education in the upcoming era is going to be completely different from the archaic education we had for a very long time. Digital technologies and the Internet are going to replace traditional classrooms. To manage the difficulties of space and time, online meetings and conferences will be conducted. Web and digital technologies will create a pool of valuable content for students, which will provide them with more exposure and better understanding. This policy envisions the promotion of research and innovation in technology-based education, which will further broaden the concept. The role of professors is going to be of utmost importance as they have to be trained for the upcoming technology-driven teaching and create awareness among the students for the adverse effects of artificial intelligence and disruptive technologies. The use of technology in education is going to create various challenges for both the institution and professors. On the one hand, technology can make studies more consuming, and it can be addictive as well. Professors need to ensure that students make the right use of technology to make them well rounded for adulthood. It will become difficult for professors to communicate with students in this type of education as technology excises social interaction; they have to be cautious as they are not making bots. The policy envisages the establishment of an autonomous body, the National Education Technology Forum (NETF), that will aid in choosing a course of action in terms of initiation and implementation of technology in education by providing the required knowledge and research to the leadership of education institutions, State and Central Governments and other Stakeholders.

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